

Molar Volumes of Some 1 : 1 Salts in Aqueous Ethyleneglycol

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The apparent molar volumes, ϕ_v , of cesium chloride, rubidium chloride, potassium sulphocyanide and tetraethylammonium halides in aqueous ethyleneglycol (20% w/w) have been estimated at 30° and 35° from the density data. The limiting apparent molar volume, ϕ_v° , has been interpreted in terms of solute-solvent interaction. Ionic molar volumes have also been estimated by determining apparent molar volumes of HCl in aqueous ethyleneglycol, and assuming $\phi_{H^+} = 0$, V° (elect.) for the ions Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , Cs^+ , Rb^+ and Et_4N^+ have been estimated. The negative V° (elect.) for the anions suggest their preferential solvation over the cations in aqueous ethyleneglycol.

INVESTIGATIONS on molar volumes of electrolytes in non-aqueous solvent systems have provided information on the nature of solute-solvent interactions¹⁻³. However similar studies in mixed solvents⁴⁻⁸ have received lesser attention. The present study has, therefore, been carried out with a view to investigate solute-solvent interaction in aqueous ethyleneglycol from the molar volume studies.

Experimental

For preparing the aqueous mixtures of ethyleneglycol, distilled water (specific conductance $\sim 10^{-6}$ Ohm⁻¹) was used. Ethyleneglycol was purified as described earlier^{9,10}. Salts used in the present study were purified by the standard methods given elsewhere¹¹. All solutions were made by weight and the conversion between the molality and molarity was done with the help of the expression given elsewhere¹². The densities of the solutions were determined with a double capillary pycnometer given elsewhere¹³. The standard deviation of the density data is ± 0.00001 units. Measurements of the densities of the solutions were made at concentration less than 0.1M. All measurements were made in an thermostat having fluctuations in temperature less than $\pm 0.02^\circ$.

Results and Discussion

The apparent molar volume, ϕ_v , is calculated from the density data using the equation¹⁴ :

$$\phi_v = \frac{1000(d_0 - d)}{C d_0} + \frac{M_2}{d_0} \quad (1)$$

where d_0 represents the density of aqueous ethyleneglycol, d the density of the salt solution, M_2 the molecular weight of the salt and C the concentration of the solution in mol l⁻¹. The molar volume,

ϕ_v , and the density of the solutions at different concentrations at 30° and 35° are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—APPARENT MOLAR VOLUMES, ϕ_v , OF Csol, Rb cl, KONS AND Et₄ NX (X=Cl⁻, Br⁻, I⁻) AND HCl IN AQUEOUS ETHYLENGLYCOL (20% W/W). (d₀=1.02800 at 30°C and d₀=1.02110 at 35°C)

Temperature (°C)	Concentration C × 10 ² (mol l ⁻¹)	Density d (g.ml ⁻¹)	ϕ_v (ml.mol ⁻¹)	ϕ_v° (ml.mol ⁻¹)
<i>Cesiumchloride</i>				
30	7.638	1.02882	88.78	144.0
	10.840	1.03751	78.14	
	15.550	1.04303	64.92	
	21.200	1.05211	53.86	
35	5.363	1.02571	80.52	200.0
	6.452	1.02732	70.80	
	7.183	1.02873	60.90	
	8.296	1.03082	50.32	
	9.709	1.03353	40.57	
<i>Rubidiumchloride</i>				
30	5.183	1.02882	196.45	390.00
	6.365	1.02402	178.75	
	7.750	1.02551	149.01	
	9.394	1.02813	116.02	
	11.524	1.02981	102.44	
35	4.559	1.01734	200.50	354.0
	6.457	1.01785	168.48	
	7.816	1.01892	155.50	
	9.027	1.02051	125.50	
	11.584	1.02272	105.50	
<i>Potassiumsulphocyanide</i>				
30	2.992	1.02971	39.50	81.0
	3.567	1.03024	34.54	
	4.201	1.03081	29.71	
	4.447	1.03102	28.92	
	6.125	1.03271	20.04	
<i>Tetraethylammoniumchloride</i>				
30	3.155	1.02843	373.14	536.0
	4.325	1.02371	350.08	
	5.596	1.02304	322.12	
	7.112	1.02432	292.43	
	8.192	1.02418	276.22	

(Table 1 Contd.)

<i>Tetraethylammoniumbromide</i>				
30	3.480	1.02404	346.24	512.0
	4.228	1.02252	330.01	
	5.411	1.02302	294.86	
	6.624	1.02323	274.92	
	7.908	1.02361	258.72	
<i>Tetraethylammoniumiodide</i>				
30	3.395	1.02504	322.09	486.0
	4.186	1.02581	301.10	
	5.276	1.02662	275.80	
	6.483	1.02761	256.01	
	7.916	1.02923	235.25	
<i>Hydrochloric acid</i>				
30	19.60	1.02332	20.61	22.0
	144.40	1.03052	18.02	
	336.40	1.03471	16.01	
	577.60	1.04071	14.00	
	921.60	1.05043	11.82	
35	19.60	1.02143	16.42	18.0
	144.40	1.02432	13.80	
	336.40	1.02932	11.82	
	577.60	1.03641	9.80	
	921.60	1.04752	7.61	

In the present study, linear plots of ϕ_V versus $\sqrt{C}$ have been obtained for all the salts in the concentration range reported here ($<0.1M$). The values of limiting apparent molar volume, ϕ_V^0 , in these solutions obtained from the extrapolation of ϕ_V versus $\sqrt{C}$ plots to $C \rightarrow 0$, are given in Table 1 alongwith ϕ_V values.

Since ϕ_V^0 has been regarded as a measure of solute-solvent interaction by many workers^{1-5,8} therefore greater magnitude of ϕ_V^0 in a solution may be regarded quantitatively as a measure of greater solute-solvent interaction.

Table 1 indicates that the magnitude of ϕ_V^0 , and therefore, solute-solvent interaction in the solutions of RbCl and CsCl in aqueous ethyleneglycol at 3° and 35° has the following order :

While following order of solute-solvent interaction is observed in case of solutions of tetraethylammonium halides :

Ionic partial molar volumes :

In an effort to have a better understanding of ion-solvent interaction in aqueous ethyleneglycol, ionic partial molar volumes have been estimated by determining the partial molar volumes with HCl, and then employing the assumption¹⁵ $\phi_{H^+}^0 = 0$ the values of the ionic-partial molar volumes were estimated and these are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—IONIC PARTIAL MOLAR VOLUMES OF Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , Cs^+ , Rb^+ AND Et_4N^+ IN AQUEOUS ETHYLENEGLYCOL (20% W/W)

Temperature (°C)	Ion	ϕ_V^0 (ml.mol ⁻¹)	$\bar{V}_0$ (elect.) (ml.mol ⁻¹)
30	Cl^-	22.0	-11.12
35	Cl^-	18.0	-15.12
30	Br^-	-2.0	-41.38
30	I^-	-28.0	-78.15
30	Cs^+	122.0	276.6
35	Cs^+	182.0	193.7
30	Rb^+	368.0	143.7
35	Rb^+	336.0	346.9
30	Et_4N^+	514	314.9

Further the partial molar volume of an ion can be assumed to be the sum of two parts, ${}^{16}\bar{V}_{int}^0$ and $\bar{V}^0$ elect.

$$\bar{V}^0_{(ion)} = \bar{V}^0_{(int)} + \bar{V}^0_{(elect)} \quad \dots (2)$$

where $\bar{V}^0_{int}$ is the intrinsic volume of the ion and $\bar{V}^0_{(elect)}$ is the volume change due to the alteration of the structure of the system by the addition of the ion, $\bar{V}^0_{int}$ has been calculated by the following equation :

$$\bar{V}^0_{int} = 2.52 (\gamma + 0.55)^3 \quad \dots (3)$$

where γ is the Pauling's radius. The radii of the various ions needed for the calculation of $\bar{V}^0_{int}$ (equation 3) were noted from the data of Yatsimirski¹⁷. The electrostriction partial molar volume of the ions calculated by using $\bar{V}^0_{ion}$ and $\bar{V}^0_{int}$ (3) are given in Table 2

Table 2 shows that the $\bar{V}^0_{elect}$ in case of Cl^- , Br^- and I^- is negative in aqueous ethyleneglycol suggesting thereby that with the addition of the ion the solvent molecules form a more compact structure around the incorporated ion resulting in the decrease in the net volume of the system^{18,19}. This is directly related to the solvation of the ion¹⁰. The positive $\bar{V}^0_{elect}$ values are obtained in case of all the cations in aqueous ethyleneglycol. This suggests that the cations are less solvated as compared to the anions in aqueous ethyleneglycol.

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